

FREQUENCY OF HEPATITIS C VIRUS IN REPEATEDLY TRANSFUSED THALASSEMIA PATIENTS

Dr. Saira Khan Wazir^{*1}, Dr. Saima Bibi²

¹Post Graduate Trainee (FCPS Pediatrics), Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad.

²Associate Professor (Study Supervisor), Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad.

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Saira Khan Wazir

Abstract

Background: Thalassemia represents a genetic and blood disorder where patients require lifelong blood transfusions; consequently, their risk for blood-transmitted infections, such as the hepatitis C virus, significantly increases. Even with recent improvements in blood screening and transfusion practices, HCV infection remains a serious problem in the case of patients with thalassemia.

Objective: To determine the frequency of HCV infection in multi-transfused thalassemia major patients.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Methodology: A total of 116 patients aged 2–15 years with thalassemia major who had received more than 10 blood transfusions were included. Hepatitis C screening was done using ELISA for anti-HCV antibodies, and positive cases were confirmed by HCV RNA testing. The prevalence of HCV infection was analyzed using statistical methods such as chi-square tests and Fisher's exact tests. The significance level was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: The study included 116 children with a mean age of 8.28 ± 3.96 years and a mean weight of 24.84 ± 8.97 kg, with 50.9% males and 49.1% females, and 53.4% from rural areas. Hepatitis C virus was detected in 11.2%, more frequently in children ≤ 10 years, those receiving over 20 transfusions, and with mothers of lower education.

Conclusion: Hepatitis C virus was detected in 11.2% of children, predominantly those aged 10 years or younger, receiving over 20 transfusions, or with mothers of lower education. These findings highlight high-risk groups, emphasizing the value of targeted screening, early intervention, and proactive management to improve pediatric health outcomes.

Introduction:

Thalassemia is an inherited blood disorder resulting from abnormal hemoglobin production, causing incurable anemia in affected individuals.¹ This condition also leads to low oxygen levels within tissues, resulting in health complications such as anemia, weak muscles, and skin discoloration due to low hemoglobin in the blood.² Those suffering from this medical condition have to undergo transfusions of blood

to keep their hemoglobin levels normal, as this will save their lives from organ or anemia-related deaths.³ Most individuals suffering from this medical condition undergo their entire life to keep their condition stable, and their lives can also go miserable due to the medical treatments they undergo along their lives for this condition.⁴ Transfusion is a very common treatment in thalassemia; in fact, it is a crucial part of managing thalassemia, especially in cases of thalassemia

major.⁵ Whenever a patient undergoes a blood transfusion, there are certain risks involved. Even though it saves a life, iron overload is a common complication of blood transfusions because it may impair the functions of certain body parts, like the heart and liver.⁶ To prevent this complication from occurring in thalassemic patients, iron chelation therapy is given to the patient to reduce excess iron in the body.⁷

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is an important issue for those living with thalassemia and undergoing multiple blood transfusions.⁸ The infection is mainly transmitted through blood contact, which increases the chances of HCV infection for those undergoing multiple transfusions.⁹ Although there have been advancements in blood screening and transfusion practices, there are cases of HCV infection among those living with thalassemia that eventually result in chronic liver conditions.¹⁰ In this patient group, there could also be progression to cirrhosis, liver failure, and even hepatocellular carcinoma due to hepatitis C infection acquired through transfused blood products.¹¹ The major issue in caring for HCV infections among those living with thalassemia occurs while balancing antiviral medications and iron-chelation therapy that has been prescribed to those living with thalassemia for many years.¹²

The study of hepatitis C virus infection in repeatedly transfused patients of thalassemia in Abbottabad has considerable importance. There has been little research work done for this purpose among this population, and it would be highly informative to define the nature of HCV among patients of thalassemia in this area. Abbottabad has a substantial population of patients with thalassemia, who religiously received blood transfusions regularly, which puts them at higher risk for acquiring HCV infections. By carrying out this research work, it will be possible to analyze the possibilities of spreading HCV infections among these patients and form strategies for its prevention.

Methodology:

This cross-sectional study was performed in the Pediatrics Unit of Ayub Teaching Hospital,

Abbottabad, from March 11, 2025, to June 11, 2025. The type of sampling technique used was consecutive non-probability sampling technique. The total sample size was calculated by the WHO sample size calculator, and the total sample size was 116 patients. The confidence interval was set at 95%, with a margin of error of 7% for a presumed prevalence of HCV infection at 18% in patients with multi-transfused thalassemia major.¹³ Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the relevant committee, and informed consent was sought from the parents or guardians of all participants, ensuring confidentiality and emphasizing that there were no risks involved in participating in the study.

The criteria of eligibility included individuals diagnosed with thalassemia major using the operational definition, belonging to between 2 and 15 years of age, and having already had over 10 transfusions of either whole blood or red blood cell components. The exclusion criteria were past splenectomy and bone marrow transplantation. The variables of demographic interest included age, gender, weight, place of residence (rural and/or urban), education of the mother, occupation of the mother, and monthly income of the family. A volume of 3 ml of venous blood was withdrawn under aseptic setup for hepatitis C virus screening and sent to the laboratory at Ayub Teaching Hospital for processing. Those individuals identified by ELISA and/or anti-HCV positivity were confirmed by nucleic acid testing for HCV RNA and labeled HCV positive.

Data analysis was carried out using SPSS version 22. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). To control for potential effect modifiers the prevalence of HCV infection was stratified by age, gender, weight, residence and mother's education. Post-stratification, the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate, was applied, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results:

The study included 116 participants with a mean age of 8.28 ± 3.96 years, of whom 69.8% were up

to 10 years old and 30.2% were above 10 years. The mean weight was 24.84 ± 8.97 kg, with 37.1% weighing ≤ 20 kg and 62.9% > 20 kg. Gender distribution was nearly equal, with 50.9% males and 49.1% females. Most participants resided in rural areas (53.4%) compared to urban areas (46.6%). Maternal education varied: 32.8% were uneducated, 43.1% had primary, 9.5% secondary, and 14.7% tertiary education. Regarding red cell concentrate transfusions, 27.6% received 10–20, 39.7% received 21–30, and 32.8% received more than 30 transfusions. Maternal occupation was predominantly skilled/professional (43.1%), followed by housewives/unemployed (33.6%) and business/other (23.3%). Family monthly income was $< 50,000$ PKR in 33.6%, $50,000-100,000$ PKR in 30.2%, and $> 100,000$ PKR in 36.2% of families. Data is given in Table 1.

The frequency of hepatitis C virus in the study population were presented in Table-II, which demonstrated that out of 116 patients, 13 patients (11.20%) tested positive for anti-HCV antibodies by ELISA, whereas 103 patients (88.80%) was negative for the infection as shown in Table-II.

The association of Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) with demographic factors was analyzed among the participants. HCV prevalence was 14.8% in children ≤ 10 years and 2.9% in those > 10 years ($p=0.105$). Among weight groups, 11.6% of children ≤ 20 kg and 11.0% of those > 20 kg tested positive ($p=1.000$). Gender-wise, 10.2% of males and 12.3% of females were HCV-positive ($p=0.775$). Rural and urban prevalence was 12.9% and 9.3%, respectively ($p=0.571$). Maternal education showed HCV in 7.9% of uneducated, 16.0% primary, 18.2% secondary, and 0% tertiary education groups ($p=0.230$). HCV prevalence increased with the number of RCC transfusions: 3.1% (10–20), 13.0% (21–30), and 15.8% (> 30) ($p=0.244$). Maternal profession and family income showed no significant association ($p=0.563$ and 0.592 , respectively). Although none of the associations were statistically significant, a higher prevalence of HCV was observed in children with lower maternal education and those receiving more than 20 transfusions, suggesting a potential trend that warrants further investigation. Data is given in Table III.

Table-I: Patient Demographics

Characteristics	Total (n=116)
Age	8.28 ± 3.96
• Upto 10 years	81 (69.8%)
• >10 years	35 (30.2%)
Weight	24.84 ± 8.97
• Upto 20 Kg	43 (37.1%)
• >20 Kg	73 (62.9%)
Gender	
• Male	59 (50.9%)
• Female	57 (49.1%)
Residence	
• Rural	62 (53.4%)
• Urban	54 (46.6%)
Education of Mother	
• Uneducated	38 (32.8%)
• Primary	50 (43.1%)
• Secondary	11 (9.5%)
• Tertiary	17 (14.7%)
Number of RCC Transfusions	

• 10-20	32 (27.6%)
• 21-30	46 (39.7%)
• >30	38 (32.8%)
Profession of Mother	
• House Wife / Unemployed	39 (33.6%)
• Skilled / Professional	50 (43.1%)
• Business / Other	27 (23.3%)
Family Monthly Income (PKR)	
• <50000	39 (33.6%)
• 50,000-100,000	35 (30.2%)
• >100,000	42 (36.2%)

Table-II: Frequency of Hepatitis C Virus in Repeatedly Transfused Thalassemia Patients

Anti HCV Antibodies (ELISA)	Frequency	% age
Yes	13	11.20%
No	103	88.80%
Total	116	100%

Table-III: Association of Hepatitis C Virus with Demographic Factors

Demographic Factors		Hepatitis C Virus		p-value
		Yes n(%)	No n(%)	
Age Group (years)	≤10	12 (14.8%)	69 (85.2%)	0.105*
	>10	1 (2.9%)	34 (97.1%)	
Weight	Upto 20 kg	5 (11.6%)	38 (88.4%)	1.000*
	>20 kg	8 (11.0%)	65 (89.0%)	
Gender	Male	6 (10.2%)	53 (89.8%)	0.775
	Female	7 (12.3%)	50 (87.7%)	
Residence	Rural	8 (12.9%)	54 (87.1%)	0.571*
	Urban	5 (9.3%)	49 (90.7%)	
Education of Mother	Uneducated	3 (7.9%)	35 (92.1%)	0.230*
	Primary	8 (16.0%)	42 (84.0%)	
	Secondary	2 (18.2%)	9 (81.8%)	
	Tertiary	0 (0.0%)	17 (100.0%)	
Number of RCC Transfusions	<20	1 (3.1%)	31 (96.9%)	0.244*
	21-30	6 (13.0%)	40 (87.0%)	
	>30	6 (15.8%)	32 (84.2%)	
Profession of Mother	House Wife / Unemployed	6 (15.4%)	33 (84.6%)	0.563*
	Skilled / Professional	5 (10.0%)	45 (90.0%)	
	Business / Other	2 (7.4%)	25 (92.6%)	
Family Monthly Income	<50000	6 (15.4%)	33 (84.6%)	0.592*
	50,000-100,000	3 (8.6%)	32 (91.4%)	
	>100,000	4 (9.5%)	38 (90.5%)	

*Fischer Exact Test

Discussion:

The current study was conducted to determine the occurrence of hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection amongst the patient cohort of thalassemia who receive multiple transfusions of blood. The data suggest that the overall HCV infection is 11.20% (n = 13/116) within the community, indicating the high occurrence of transfusion-linked infections amongst the at-risk population of thalassemia patients. This occurrence could be attributed to the life-long need for frequent transfusions that increase the overall chances of infection through the use of possibly contaminated blood supplies. Even with the available screening programs for infection prevention, the occurrence window for HCV infection and the already set limitations for detection procedures might enable the transfusion of possibly contaminated units and the subsequent spreading of the infection amongst recipients. Despite the absence of statistical significance for the link between transfusion and infection (p = 0.244), there was a clear trend towards increasing infection risks with increased transfusion, where individuals who have undergone more transfusions revealed higher infection risks. In individuals with more than 30 transfusions, the positivity rate was 15.8% (n = 6/38), whilst for individuals who have undergone transfusions ranging from 10–20 transfusions the positivity rate was 3.1% (n = 1/32). This trend is reflective of the dose-response relationship regarding overall risks for infection related to the potential transfusion supplies that directly increase the risks for infection by probably encountering the possibly contaminated supplies on multiple occasions.

The present study found HCV prevalence of 11.20% (n=13/116) among repeatedly transfused thalassemia patients which was relatively lower compared to several studies from Pakistan and Iraq. This finding were comparable with Hassan *et al.*¹⁴ who reported 10.86% prevalence in Iraqi thalassemia patients and Nadir *et al.*¹⁵ who documented 9.3% HBsAg positivity, though their HCV rate was higher at 31.7%. Similarly, Syed *et al.* reported it the frequency of HCV in our study

was 37 (18.5%). HCV was significantly associated the number of blood transfusion < 7.¹⁶ However, current results was substantially lower than Ahmed *et al.*¹⁷ who reported 18.3% anti-HCV positivity in Baluchistan and Ullah *et al.*¹⁸ who found 23.8% HCV prevalence in Peshawar. The most striking difference was observed with Akhtar *et al.*¹⁹ systematic review which revealed pooled HCV prevalence of 36.2% across Pakistan, with regional variations showing Punjab at 46% being highest. These variations in prevalence rates can be attributed to differences in blood safety standards, implementation of screening protocols, and availability of nucleic acid testing (NAT) across different regions and time periods. The lower prevalence in present study may reflect improved donor screening practices and better blood bank regulation in recent years compared to earlier studies. Regarding age-related patterns, current study showed higher positivity in younger patients ≤10 years with 14.8% (n=12/81) compared to 2.9% (n=1/35) in older patients >10 years, though this was not statistically significant (p=0.105). This finding were contradictory to most previous studies where older age was associated with higher infection rates. Ahmed *et al.*¹⁷ reported infected children being significantly older (13.2 vs 6 years, P<0.001), while Ullah *et al.*¹⁸ demonstrated age-specific HCV rates rising from 7.9% in 0.5-3 years to 31% in 15-19 years age group. Similarly, Hassan *et al.*¹⁴ found highest rate of 37.25% in 30-34 years age group with no infection in children ≤4 years, and Altaf & Hussain¹⁶ showed sharp rise after 10 years with HCV positivity increasing from 6.5% to 83% (P<0.001).

The current study demonstrated no significant gender difference with males showing 10.2% (n=6/59) and females 12.3% (n=7/57) positivity (p=0.775), which were consistent with findings of Siyal *et al.*²⁰ who reported equal infection rates in males and females (9 each out of 18 positive cases). Hassan *et al.*¹⁴ also found similar rates between males (11.14%) and females (10.51%). However, Ullah *et al.*¹⁸ reported higher male predominance with 83.3% of HBV cases and 62.8% of HCV cases being males, though this may reflect higher

proportion of males in their study population (63%). These findings support that HCV transmission through transfusion were independent of gender as biological susceptibility do not vary significantly between sexes. Regarding transfusion burden, present study showed trend of increasing infection with higher number of transfusions, though not statistically significant ($p=0.244$), with rates rising from 3.1% ($n=1/32$) in 10-20 transfusions to 15.8% ($n=6/38$) in >30 transfusions. This pattern was consistent with multiple studies demonstrating strong association between transfusion frequency and infection risk. Ahmed *et al.*¹⁷ reported infected children receiving mean 264 transfusions versus 96 in uninfected ($P<0.001$), while Ullah *et al.*¹⁸ found mean transfusions being significantly higher in HCV-positive patients ($P=0.001$). Nadir *et al.*¹⁵ demonstrated most striking difference with 0% HBV positivity in <8 transfusions versus 17.8% in ≥ 8 transfusions ($P<0.001$) and HCV rates of 18.9% versus 43.3% respectively ($P<0.001$).

The research has various limitations that need to be acknowledged. Firstly, this study is a single-center study where data is collected in only one setting. This could make generalization of results for other study participants a limitation. The study population included only 116 participants. The sample size could make results unreliable because a smaller sample size could make finding significant results difficult. The study has a cross-sectional research design where there is no possibility to study the relationship between cause and effect. The study only uses ELISA for testing HCV. There could have been false-negative results.

Conclusion:

Hepatitis C virus was detected in 11.2% of children, predominantly those aged 10 years or younger, receiving over 20 transfusions, or with mothers of lower education. These findings highlight high-risk groups, emphasizing the value of targeted screening, early intervention, and proactive management to improve pediatric health outcomes.

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Ethical Approval:

This research received approval from the Ethical Committee. It was conducted in accordance with the committee's guidelines and the Helsinki Declaration.

Patients' Consent:

All participants provided written consent before joining the study. They were informed that their personal data would remain confidential and they could withdraw from the study at any point.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this study.

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2

Substantial contributions to concept, study design Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

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